

NP-complete Problems can be Solved and Verified in Polynomial Time

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ABSTRACT

In this short paper we give the final resolution of “P versus NP” theorem according to our previous results obtained in the field of automaton implementation for extended regular expressions and generally intersection operator.

Keywords: P versus NP, proof, P = NP.

INTRODUCTION

The statement was given before by Stephen Cook [1] in his seminal work, where there’s a clear definition of oracle with ‘certificate’ and the problem solution itself defined as an automaton.

Prior to this ‘milestone work’, we have worked on narratives of experimental proof and showed that the equivalence function exists [2], this is, however, not a definitive answer with the full composition of the problem according to oracle and problem languages.

Before we have shown that intersection of languages can be simulated on finite automaton with the ‘witness state’ [3-5].

STATEMENT

Let’s define the language proposed by our solution as $L_{solution}(A)$, where A is the alphabet and also let’s define the language recognized by set of oracles as $L_{oracle}(A)$ over the same alphabet.

We are to show that P equals NP and, thus, the problem can be solved and verified in any polynomial time.

PROOF

Let’s assume that P not equals NP and thus, we have:

$$t\{L_{solution}(A)\} \gg t\{L_{oracle}(A)\}.$$

For our proof let’s assume that states in our solution automaton with oracles are final states as they are actually accepting any existing problem solution.

As we know the only condition in order for the arbitrary word w to be a solution is defined as:

$$w \in L_{solution}(A) \wedge w \in L_{oracle}(A).$$

From the above it follows that:

$$w \in [L_{solution}(A) \cap L_{oracle}(A)].$$

Let’s construct the modified state automaton for the intersection of the languages above as it was first stated in [3-5] – this algorithm shows that we have the least number of operations in order to compute by our algorithm:

$$t(w) = \max[|L_{solution}(A)|, |L_{oracle}(A)|] = |L_{solution}(A)| = O(|w|^k).$$

From the above it follows that the time for solving the co-existence of certificate path and path followed by solution branch in our automaton construction is polynomial, thus the languages can be found on both paths of our branching, since our automaton is finite.

Thus it follows that complexity classes are equal:

$$P = NP.$$

DISCUSSION

Generally speaking, we have already shown the thesis on whether any non-deterministic finite automaton can be as functional as any deterministic one – since we have a strong proof of the linear complexity of our algorithm on non-deterministic automaton [5], it follows that it's as performing as on deterministic automaton [3, 4].

The above proof could be possible when even simulating automaton, however, we apply the intersection as we have in general the set of certifying states which is polynomial as it was stated in the original theorem [1].

CONCLUSION

We have shown the proof the equivalence of general complexity classes by our finite automaton construction for intersection operator and the way of its simulation which is to be linear. For better understanding of our methodology, it's recommended to read our algorithm in the reference articles, which is omitted here as it was outlined many times before with the general aim of implementation of effective solutions on finite automaton with extended operators like intersection, subtraction and complement.

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We express our sympathy towards effective algorithms and their verification as it goes beyond 'extended operators' and, thus, gives a more broader sense towards proof of "P versus NP" theorem.

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